

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Zhao, J., Wei, C., & Li, J. (2022). Is the research performance of Chinese returnees better than that of their local counterparts?. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators, STI 2022* (sti22158).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6962388>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Is the research performance of Chinese returnees better than that of their local counterparts?

Jingyi Zhao*, Chunli Wei* and Jiang Li*

*zhaojingyi100@163.com; weichunli1998@outlook.com; lijiang@nju.edu.cn

School of Information Management, Nanjing University, Xianlin Street, Nanjing, China

Abstract: Chinese government issued a series of policies to attract oversea elites and gave them privileges in research, which aroused complaints from domestic scientists in the past decades. Therefore, the research performance of returnees and their local counterparts has been widely discussed. We selected 4,770 returnees and their local counterparts employed by the same departments of the same institutions in the same year from 1984 to 2017, and compared their research performance by regression analysis. Results show: (1) returnees have no significant advantages in publishing more papers or first-tier journal papers, but more corresponding author papers in the fields of Sciences; and (2) for the fields of Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences, returnees still have advantages in publishing more papers and more first-tier journal papers.

Keywords: Returnees; Domestic scientists; Academic performance; Fixed-effect model

Introduction

Chinese academia has been experiencing a structural shift from a local scientist-dominated system to a local-returnees hybrids system in the past decades. Since the 1980s, China experienced a brain drain, which means a large number of students went abroad for further studies, and a small number of them returned to China after graduation, although Chinese governments issued many policies to attract them back along with the booming of China's economy (Cao et al., 2020; Jonkers & Tijssen, 2008; Yan et al., 2015). Till 2008, the Chinese central government announced the "Thousand Talents Program" and in the following two years, the program grew to encompass younger talent under the age of 40 (Jia, 2018). All successful applicants can gain a one million yuan starting bonus and have the chance to apply for a research fund of 3-5 million yuan. The policies successfully attracted 1,510 talents, and 77% of them were innovative talents by the end of 2011 and made great contributions to the brain gain in China by being followed by local governments. Consequently, over 3.1 million, or 83.7 percent of Chinese overseas students who had completed their tertiary or post-graduate studies, returned to China by 2017 (Cao et al., 2020).

The policy for attracting returnees has given them privileges, such as sufficient fees for settlement, more research funding, and priority promotion opportunities, which have created a gap in career development between returnees and the local scientists, and aroused complaints from local scientists. An interview shows that 21% of local scientists feel that returnees have excessive privileges in obtaining national academic resources: local scientists receive much less

research funding than returnees; there are three times more local scientists who are "not very satisfied" with their housing than returnees; returnees were promoted much faster. Some PhD returnees are immediately promoted to full professorships, which upsets their local counterparts because they have yet to prove themselves capable of independent research (Zweig, 2006). Furthermore, the requirement of "overseas returnee only" from the recruit notices of universities and research institutions upset local PhD students, whatever they have achieved (Chen, 2022). To survive the competition with the returnees, the Chinese government financially supports local scientists and PhD students to visit foreign universities/institutions as visiting scholars/students from six months to two years to help them build international collaboration. Many local PhD students also go overseas for Postdoc positions to obtain overseas experiences immediately after graduation, which are required by most Chinese universities for recruitment and promotion. Considering the preferences for overseas PhDs in Chinese universities and research institutions, we propose the following research question:

Is the research performance of Chinese returnees better than that of their local counterparts?

Data and methodology

Data

We collected the data from the ORCID website and the Web of Science (WoS) database. The former is a unique 16-digit author identifier that is randomly assigned to each author, which helps disambiguate authors and contributes to the research of scholarly activities (Akers et al., 2016). By the end of 2017, ~0.75 million academic profiles of each registrant were displayed on the web page www.orcid.org.

Using the profiles of scientists on the ORCID website, we first selected ~20,000 scientists who are native Chinese, have PhD degrees, and at least an employment experience. We presumed the nationalities of scientists based on the first degrees that they obtained according to the records in ORCID. Then, we distinguished the returnees who meet the following criteria,

- a) s/he has a PhD degree from a place other than mainland China. Besides, the overseas experience should last at least two years. If a scientist has more than one PhDs, we used the one which takes more years to identify the country s/he received his PhD degree, and
- b) s/he returned back to China and was employed by a university or a research institute, excluding employment as Postdoc researcher.

We defined the local counterparts of a returnee as follows,

- a) they obtained their PhDs from a place in mainland China, and
- b) they are employed by the same departments of the same institutions in the same year as the returnee.

As a result, our dataset comprises 637 returnees and 4,133 local counterparts to be compared. Next, we searched for their publications in the WoS Core Collection as their research performance. The GIPP discipline scheme system is applied to identify scientists' disciplines, which include Clinical, Pre-Clinical & Health, Engineering & Technology, Life Sciences, Physical Sciences, Social Sciences, and Arts & Humanities. Specifically, the discipline of each scientist is determined by the institutions they affiliate to. For example, a scientist belongs to economics if their affiliation is the Department of Economics, then s/he belongs to Social Sciences according to the GIPP discipline.

Methods

In this study, the research performance of a scientist is measured by

- a) the average number of papers s/he published in a five-year period,
- b) the average number of first-tier journal papers (defined by the Chinese Academy of Sciences) s/he published in a five-year period, and
- c) the average number of corresponding author papers s/he published in a five-year period.

The dependent, independent variable and control variables are defined as follows:

a) Dependent variables

P_n : for a returnee, it is the average number of papers s/he published per year in continuous five years since his/her return. For his/her local counterparts, it is the average number of papers s/he published per year in continuous five years since the returnee's return.

P_{ft} : same to P_n , but refers to the average number of first-tier journal papers.

P_c : same to P_n , but refers to the average number of corresponding author papers.

b) Independent variables

$Is_oversea$: whether a scientist obtains a PhD degree from overseas. It equals 1 if yes; otherwise, 0.

c) Control variables

P_{ft-b} : the annual number of first-tier journal papers published before the return year.

P_{n-b} : the annual number of papers published before the return year.

$Start_Year$: the year a returnee returned.

$Institution_Class$: the institution a scientist belongs to. Chinese Government allocates more funding to elite universities, like Project 985 and Project 211 (Quan et al., 2017). Thus, the institution brings different resources for scientists who promote academic performance. The fixed effect of the institution is necessary when observing two groups of scientists.

$Department_Class$: The department a scientist belongs to. It values the department scientists belong to, at the same time, stands for the discipline of academics. The development of different subjects is still asymmetrical in China (Zhou & Leydesdorff, 2006; Ai, 2019), with strengths in physics and Chemistry and weaknesses in Social Sciences. Academic resources distribute unevenly across different areas, so scientists in the same discipline are comparable.

A fixed-effect model was built to control the unobserved heterogeneity in regression (Mummolo & Peterson, 2018). The model takes the following form:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Is_oversea + \beta_2 P_{ft-b} + \beta_3 P_{n-b} + \beta_4 Start_Year + \beta_5 Institution_Class + \beta_6 Department_Class + e_1, \quad (1)$$

where β_0, \dots, β_6 are unknown coefficients, and e_1 represents the error term.

Results

Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables in our dataset, consisting of 4,770 returnees and local scientists.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
P_n	4,770	1.540	2.896	0	61.2
P_{ft}	4,770	0.388	1.080	0	26.2
P_c	4,770	0.328	0.822	0	17.2
P_{nb}	4,770	3.941	11.547	0	413
P_{ftb}	4,770	0.949	3.949	0	184

Regression Results

Table 2 presents the relationship between an overseas PhD of a scientist and his/her research performance. $Is_oversea$ positively affects P_c , and there is no significant difference between it and P_n and P_{ft} . In other words, returnees and local scientists have similar academic performance in the total number of publications and first-tier journal papers. However, returnees published more articles as corresponding authors than their domestic counterparts, with a difference of 0.134 ($p < 0.01$) papers.

Table 2. Fixed effect Regression of research performance

VARIABLES	(1) P_n	(2) P_c	(3) P_{ft}
$is_Oversea$	-0.021 (0.137)	0.134*** (0.051)	-0.027 (0.054)
P_{n-b}	0.135*** (0.006)	0.031*** (0.002)	0.014*** (0.002)
P_{ft-b}	0.053*** (0.018)	-0.019*** (0.007)	0.138*** (0.007)
Constant	1.023*** (0.047)	0.237*** (0.018)	0.221*** (0.018)
$Start_Year$	Y	Y	Y
$Institution_Class$	Y	Y	Y
$Department_Class$	Y	Y	Y
Observations	4,770	4,770	4,770
R-squared	0.610	0.356	0.609

Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

We also found that scientists in different disciplines have different research performances. Table 3 shows that returnees in the fields of Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences have significant advantages in the number of publications and first-tier publications. In other words, returnees published 0.742 more papers and 0.380 more first-tier papers per year than their local counterparts, respectively. There is no significant difference between the two groups of scientists for the number of corresponding authors.

Table 3. Regression results in the fields of Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences

VARIABLES	(1) P_n	(2) P_c	(3) P_{ft}
<i>is_Oversea</i>	0.742* (0.412)	0.148 (0.195)	0.380*** (0.137)
P_{n-b}	0.369*** (0.077)	0.096** (0.036)	0.046* (0.026)
P_{ft-b}	0.150 (0.234)	0.122 (0.110)	0.169** (0.078)
<i>Constant</i>	0.135 (0.156)	0.132* (0.074)	-0.041 (0.052)
<i>Start_Year</i>	Y	Y	Y
<i>Institution_Class</i>	Y	Y	Y
<i>Department_Class</i>	Y	Y	Y
<i>Observations</i>	407	407	407
<i>R-squared</i>	0.763	0.749	0.656

Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table 4. Regression results in the fields of Sciences (including Clinical, Pre-Clinical & Health, Engineering & Technology, Life Sciences, and Physical Sciences)

VARIABLES	(1) P_n	(2) P_c	(3) P_{ft}
<i>is_Oversea</i>	-0.051 (0.148)	0.133** (0.055)	-0.042 (0.059)
P_{n-b}	0.133*** (0.006)	0.031*** (0.002)	0.014*** (0.003)
P_{ft-b}	0.059*** (0.019)	-0.018** (0.007)	0.138*** (0.007)
<i>Constant</i>	1.068*** (0.050)	0.240*** (0.019)	0.234*** (0.020)
<i>Start_Year</i>	Y	Y	Y
<i>Institution_Class</i>	Y	Y	Y
<i>Department_Class</i>	Y	Y	Y
<i>Observations</i>	4,364	4,364	4,364
<i>R-squared</i>	0.611	0.357	0.609

Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

The returnees in Sciences (the other four GIPP disciplines) have significant advantages in corresponding author publications. In other words, returnees have more chances of being principal investigators (PI) than their local counterparts. However, returnees have no advantages in the total number of publications and first-tier publications.

Discussions and Conclusions

It is verified in this study that returnees do not have significant advantages in publishing more papers or more first-tier journal papers than their local counterparts in the same departments of the same institutions, although they have many privileges. We firstly explored the effect of an oversea PhD of a scientist on his/her research performance by sampling 4,770 returnees and their local counterparts who were employed by the same departments of the same institutions in the same year during 1984-2017. We found that returnees have significant advantages in publishing corresponding author papers than their local counterparts, which indicates that they have more chances of being PI of research teams. This advantage did not exist in the fields of Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences, but in the fields of Sciences. However, we also found that returnees have neither a significant advantage in publishing more papers nor more first-tier journal papers. But when it comes to Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences, returnees still have advantages in publishing more papers and more first-tier papers.

The gap between returnees and their local counterparts has been narrowed significantly so far. In 2020, the State Council of the PRC issued a policy, "General Program for Deepening Educational Evaluation Reform in the New Era" to balance returnees and their local counterparts, which points out that universities should not take oversea experiences as the requirements of employment or promotion. Thus, the recruitment in two top universities adopted a non-preferential stance toward applicants' academic credentials (Chen, 2022).

Returnees have a clear publication advantage in Arts & Humanity and Social Science, while domestic scientists perform better in Sciences as PIs. The difference is drawn from the unbalanced development of disciplines. In the field of Sciences, China is undergoing a continued and significant increase in scientific production (Jin & Rousseau, 2005; Zhou & Leydesdorff, 2006) and has taken a world-leading position in several subfields of chemistry and physics (Zhou et al., 2009; Malarvizhi et al., 2010). However, the low priority of Social Science in the early period caused the slower development in China, which is yet to take off on the international stage (Ai, 2019). It is considered that China's humanities and social sciences (HSS) experienced the "preparing phase" (1956-1978), "introducing in" (1978-the 1990s), domestic practice (1990-2000s), and "going global" (after 2000) stages during the development (Li & Li, 2015). Although China's HSS is in line with international academic norms and becoming innovative, it is still not a major player in Social Sciences. We are continuously facing the problems of limited regional authorship, lack of individuality, and the low international visibility and citation shares of publication (Liu et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2009; Wang, 2008).

One of the limitations to this study is that the findings are generated from ORCID, which skews young scientists. The other is that the distribution of disciplines based on the ORCID dataset is uneven, with a large percentage of scientists in Engineering & Technology and a low percentage in Arts & Humanities.

References

- Ai, B. (2019). Pains and gains of working in Chinese universities: An academic returnee's journey. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 38(4), 661–673.
- Akers, K. G., Sarkozy, A., Wu, W., & Slyman, A. (2016). ORCID Author Identifiers: A Primer for Librarians. *Medical Reference Services Quarterly*, 35(2), 135–144.

- Cao, C., Baas, J., Wagner, C. S., & Jonkers, K. (2020). Returning scientists and the emergence of China's science system. *Science and Public Policy*, 47(2), 172–183.
- Chen, N. (2022). 'Why should a "foreigner" be better than me?': Preferential practices in junior academic faculty recruitment among mainland Chinese universities. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 28(1), 17–41.
- Jia, H. (2018). What Is China's Thousand Talents Plan? *Nature*, 553(7688), S8–S8.
- Jin, B. H., & Rousseau, R. (2005). China's quantitative expansion phase: Exponential growth but low impact. In P. Ingwersen & B. Larsen (Eds.), *ISSI 2005: Proceedings of the 10th International Conference of the International Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics, Vols 1 and 2* (pp. 362–370). Karolinska Univ Press Ab. <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/allldb/full-record/WOS:000232759800047>
- Jonkers, K., & Tijssen, R. (2008). Chinese researchers returning home: Impacts of international mobility on research collaboration and scientific productivity. *Scientometrics*, 77(2), 309–333.
- Li, J., & Li, Y. (2015). Patterns and evolution of coauthorship in China's humanities and social sciences. *Scientometrics*, 102(3), 1997–2010.
- Liu, W., Hu, G., Tang, L., & Wang, Y. (2015). China's global growth in social science research: Uncovering evidence from bibliometric analyses of SSCI publications (1978-2013). *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(3), 555–569.
- Malarvizhi, R., Wang, M. H., & Ho, Y. S. (2010). Research trends in adsorption technologies for dye containing wastewaters. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 8, 930–942.
- Mummolo, J., & Peterson, E. (2018). Improving the Interpretation of Fixed Effects Regression Results. *Political Science Research and Methods*, 6(4), 829–835.
- Quan, W., Chen, B., & Shu, F. (2017). Publish or impoverish An investigation of the monetary reward system of science in China (1999-2016). *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 69(5), 486–502.
- Wang, F. N. (2008). Problems and solutions for social science journals at Chinese universities. *Journal of Scholarly Publishing*, 39(4), 410–416.
- Yan, G., Yue, Y., & Niu, M. (2015). An empirical study of faculty mobility in China. *Higher Education*, 69(4), 527–546. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-014-9789-y>
- Zhou, P., & Leydesdorff, L. (2006). The emergence of China as a leading nation in science. *Research Policy*, 35(1), 83–104.
- Zhou, P., Thijs, B., & Glaenzel, W. (2009). Is China also becoming a giant in social sciences? *Scientometrics*, 79(3), 593–621.
- Zweig, D. (2006). Competing for talent: China's strategies to reverse the brain drain. *International Labour Review*, 145(1–2), 65–+.

